

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN TOURISM

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7176292>

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Abstract : *Digitalisation is changing the way people live, work, and travel, and has opened up new opportunities for tourism businesses to compete in global markets. This chapter examines the impact of digitalisation on tourism, with a particular focus on SMEs.*

Keywords: *digital economy, tourism industry, hotels, demand and supply, information technology, employment*

In our country, the state is taking measures to develop the digital part of the economy, including each of its sectors. These include the implementation of a number of information technologies, such as remote communication, the introduction of electronic document the development of electronic payments, the improvement of the regulatory framework in the field of e-commerce. That's why blockchain technology, artificial intelligence, and the use of supercomputers are so important today. One of the countries around the world is to work on crypto introduced not only to sectors of the economy, but also to the public administration system and other public relations.

Digital economy is based on electronic goods and services produced by an electronic business and traded through electronic commerce, a business with electronic production and management processes and that interacts with its partners and customers and conducts transactions through Internet and Web technologies. With growing population and resource mobilization, digital economy is not limited to business trading and services effecting on every aspect of life from health to education and from business to banking. Many observers have noted the rapid growth of the broadly defined digital economy [1-12]. Much attention is being paid to the ongoing and dramatic growth in electronic or e-commerce. In spite of its rapid growth in recent years, we view the emergence of e-commerce as an important trend that is only part of the more general changing structure of the economy brought on by the dramatic changes in information technology. One of the goals of the introduction of the digital economy in the field of tourism, as mentioned above, is to eliminate the elements of the shadow

economy in the industry. It is important to note that this economy has many positive aspects, as well as the ability to curb the shadow economy.

The definitions of tourism innovation (such as product, service and technological innovations) remains unclear, with the exception maybe of the Internet. New technologies can produce an essential contribution to tourism development. For tourism businesses, the Internet offers the potential to make information and booking facilities available to large numbers of tourists at relatively low costs. It also provides a tool for communication between tourism suppliers, intermediaries, as well as end-consumers. According to WTO, the Internet is revolutionizing the distribution of tourism information and sales. An increasing proportion of Internet users are buying on-line and tourism will gain a larger and larger share of the online commerce market.

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Tourism is one of the fastest growing and most important economic sectors in the world providing benefits to both host communities and destination areas. The definitions of tourism innovation (such as product, service and technological innovations) remains unclear, with the exception maybe of the Internet. New technologies can produce an essential contribution to tourism development. For tourism businesses, the Internet offers the potential to make information and booking facilities available to large numbers of tourists at relatively low costs. It also provides a tool for communication between tourism suppliers, intermediaries, as well as end-consumers. According to WTO, the Internet is revolutionizing the distribution of tourism information and sales. An increasing proportion of Internet users are buying on-line and tourism will gain a larger and larger share of the online commerce market.

The terms “digital economy,” “information technology,” and “electronic commerce” do not have standard definitions [25-30]. When referring to information technology, we will be referring to information processing and related

equipment, software, semiconductors, and telecommunications equipment. References to electronic commerce will mean the use of the Internet to sell goods and services. We interpret digital economy as including both information technology and electronic commerce.

The tourism sector is challenged by a growing demand for customer orientation, increasing international competition, volatile markets in an insecure environment, changing customer demands towards individualization and significant potential in various market segments. Furthermore, it is vitally important for the sector to be able to attract the labor force trained specifically for work in tourism. The problem was noted that some employers deliberately look for unqualified labor for the sake of paying less.

The question, however, remains whether such a policy would lead to higher profits and longer-term competitiveness. Another important question remains: how can the skill gaps in the tourism sector be overcome under the condition of insecure and often seasonal employment and relatively low pay? Over the past six decades, tourism has experienced continued growth and diversification to become one of the largest and fastest growing economic sectors in the world. Over time, more and more destinations have opened up and invested in tourism development, turning modern tourism into a key driver for socioeconomic progress. Today export incomes generated by international tourism ranks fourth after fuels, chemicals and automotive products. For many developing countries, it is one of the main income sources and the number one export category, creating much needed employment and opportunities for development.

Travel and tourism are now the largest generators of jobs, accounting for about 11% of the global workforce. The economic impact of tourism is aptly demonstrated by its relative contribution to GDP, foreign exchange earnings and employment opportunities. Where tourism is well integrated into the tourism economy, the job creation prospects are good. Good transport infrastructure is critical for the development of tourism. Globally, the airline transport market has continued to expand and this trend is expected to continue. Air traffic control and safety at many regional airports are poor by international standards and require upgrading in terms of both equipment and staff. The problem areas require improved telecommunications infrastructure and satellitebased navigation.

The tourism industry generates substantial economic benefits to both host countries and tourists' home countries. It is an especially important industry to developing countries. The main benefits of tourism to a country are foreign exchange earnings, tax revenues, business opportunities for budding

entrepreneurs, and employment for workers in the industry. According to the WTO, "Tourism is one of the top five export categories for as many as 83% of countries and is the main source of foreign exchange earnings for at least 38% of countries." Foreign exchange earnings from exports are used to purchase imports and augment reserves. They generate income in the host country and can stimulate consumer spending and investment in other sectors of the economy.

Digital technologies and platforms are disrupting the way the tourism sector operates from end to end. Digital platforms offer global access to consumers and allow service providers to enhance the development of the tourism sector and its competitive standards. Many low-income economies can potentially benefit from this digital transformation and others are at risk of being left behind if they fail to embrace this moment.

In conclusion, the above recommendations suggest that the development of digital tourism in our country in a pandemic environment will ensure the safety of tourists, sustainable development of the industry, prevent corruption and the shadow economy, and create a fair sector. The digitalization of the tourism industry not only makes the tourism business more flexible, but also increases the competitiveness of the industry based on digital technologies.

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